

Ubuntulisation Of Mathematics Classroom For The Enhancement Of Learner's Interest And Achievement

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The greatest problem faced by mathematics teachers and learners in Africa is the wholly adoption of the strategies, techniques and concepts relating to the teaching and learning of mathematics as a subject. A struggle out of this ugly situation has birthed the ethnomathematics, which is yet to be adopted in most of the countries in Africa. Recently, there has been a new aspect of mathematics developed which is known as Social Justice Mathematics, a concept which is not different from Ubuntu which has being a guiding principle when it comes to equality and justice in all facets of human life. Instead of completely adopting social justice mathematics as a contemporary remedy for the enhancement of students' interest and achievement in mathematics, it is better to Africanise the remedy by applying ubuntu as a replacement of the above for maximum achievement by learners. The paper has done justice to the concepts of ethnomathematics, social justice mathematics, ubuntu and ubuntulisation of mathematics classroom with relevant examples aimed at bringing the mathematics teachers back to Africa in the planning and teaching of mathematics to learners.

Key words: *Mathematics Classroom, Ubuntu, Achievement, Interest, Social Justice Mathematics*

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Introduction

The greatest problem faced by mathematics teachers and learners in Africa is the wholly adoption of the strategies, techniques and concepts relating to the teaching and learning of mathematics as a subject. A struggle out of this ugly situation has birthed the ethnomathematics, which is yet to be adopted in most of the countries in Africa. Ethnomathematics is refer to as the relationship between culture and mathematics (D'Ambrosio, 2001; D' Ambrosio, 1985).During a 1977 presentation to the American Association for the Advancement of Science, Brazilian mathematician, and educator UbiratanD'Ambrosio coined the term "ethnomathematics"(Age and Akaazua, 2021).The basic objective of ethnomathematics is to foster an appreciation of the relationships between mathematics and culture, while also contributing to both fields of study.Although the term may not be recognizable to many Mathematics educators, having a rudimentary understanding of it enables educators to broaden their perspectives on mathematics and provide students with more effective instruction.

Ethnomathematics

Many scholars have grappled with the meaning of the term since D'Ambrosio coined it, including himself. ("An etymological abuse leads D'Ambrosio to use the word *ethnoto* refer to Ethnic" or "cultural context" and *mathemato* mean "to explain" or "to know" or "understand" and *tics* from "techne") (Age and Akaazua, 2021). Ethnomathematics according to Omenka (2013), is the study and recording of learning styles that are culturally specific. The study of mathematics among recognizable cultural groupings, such as labour groups, national-tribal communities, age-specific kid populations, professional classes, and so forth, is known as ethnomathematics (D'Ambrosio, 1985).Ethnomathematics is seen as the study of mathematics' cultural dimensions. Rosa and Orey (2011) opine that ethnomathematics explains curricular mathematical ideas in a way that connects them to the students' every day and cultural experiences, strengthening their capacity to make meaningful connections and expanding their comprehension of the subject. With this explanation, the teaching and learning of mathematics should be based on the culture, beliefs, norms and values of the learners concerned. Africa is a multicultural continent with diverse culture and beliefs depending on the location within the continent. For example, in south Africa, teaching an expression $x + y = x + y$ or $a + b = a + b$ to a learner in Venda (Limpopo Province) will make more meaning if you make use of items which are readily found within their community or environment to remove the abstract nature of the mathematics. The Venda

people are known to produce fruits, therefore using fruits in place of the alphabets x and y will be more encompassing and meaningful. Let your x be an apple and y a mango fruit. i.e., *Apple + mango* will still give you *Apple + mango*. Since the learners are familiar with these fruits its easier for them to understand what you are trying to explain than using mere alphabets. Adding an apple and mango still gives you apple and mango same as adding x and y still gives you x and y , same applies to $x-y = x-y$. Another good example is when teaching angle of elevation with a question such as “a man standing on a tower, spot a fruit...”

A learner in a typical village at this point will be struggling to understand what a tower is, before coming back to understand the question itself. Assuming a palm tree was used in place of the tower it would have been very easy for the learner to understand the question, since the learner is already familiar with the palm tree in the locality. These and many other examples have shown that when the teaching and learning of mathematics is done using objects within the locality it aids in the understanding of mathematics, thus, paving way for an improved performance. Each group of people have their own culture and beliefs and its pertinent to take into cognisance the environment and the way of life of the learners so as to bring about meaning learning. According to Rosa and Orey (2008), ethnomathematics makes use of these cultural experiences to give students insights into how mathematics is rooted in their social and cultural contexts and to make mathematics learning more relevant. Machaba and Dhlamini (2021) The study of ethnomathematics focuses on the relationship between a culture and mathematics and how understanding a culture can improve a person's mathematical understanding. Ensign (2003) opines that teaching that is culturally relevant uses cultural referents to convey knowledge, skills, and attitudes while also empowering students politically, socially, emotionally, and intellectually.

This is the more reason why every concept developed in the field of mathematics should have its corresponding versions developed based on the cultural belief of the learners. Recently there have been an agitation that mathematics classrooms should be operated with equity and justice so to enhance the performance of learners in mathematics at all levels of education, and this is also referred to as social justice mathematics.

Social Justice Mathematics (SJM)

Angle of Depression

Social justice mathematics is aimed at equipping students to recognise and address injustice outside of the classroom in addition to fostering equity within the mathematics classroom. One of the main issues facing mathematics educators is achieving equity in the classroom. (NCTM, 2000). The social, political, and economic power structures in society are closely related to education and contribute to the persistence of inequality in both society and schools. (Kozol, 2005). Education is meant to transform society so that everyone is included, not to help the excluded become more integrated into the mainstream. Consequently, teaching and learning of mathematics ought to assist learners in examining oppression and critiquing injustices, emphasizing the relevance of these concerns to their own lives and motivating them to confront such unjust systems (Bartell, 2013). When discussing equity in the teaching and learning of mathematics, people always refer to improved resources, advanced courses, and more equitable access to high-inequality mathematics instruction. The goal of mathematics for social justice is to apply insights from critical mathematics pedagogy and related educational philosophies to the teaching of mathematics at all levels of education. Alvarez (2019) notes that “*Social justice is about treating all pupils equally and allocating resources in a way that makes them feel safe and comfortable both physically and mentally.*” From the available research, teaching mathematics for social justice has been shown to have two educational goals: (i) giving all pupils excellent mathematics instruction; and (ii) encouraging the growth of social political consciousness and practice through

mathematics study. When the issue of injustice and inequality in the mathematics classroom is dealt with by mathematics teachers, students' interest in mathematics will be enhanced, thus, improving the performance of students in mathematics. When creating mathematical learning experiences for students, mathematics teachers should adhere to the six pedagogical principles for teaching social justice highlighted by Cochran-Smith (2004) which includes (i) facilitate meaningful work within learning groups (ii) expand on the knowledge that students bring to the class (iii) fill in gaps and impart skills. (iv) work with people, families and communities; not against them (v) expand the variety of evaluation methods (vi) include clear curricular components on activism, power and inequality.

Benefits of Social Justice to Mathematics Learning

Several benefits have been identified because of using social justice mathematics approach in the teaching and learning of mathematics at the various levels of education. Teachers must strive to close opportunity inequalities that fuel achievement discrepancies, dispel misconceptions about mathematics, effectively educate their pupils for future aspirations, and dispel the myth that mathematics is a subject reserved for a select few (Huinker et al., 2020). Teaching mathematics for social justice entails applying mathematical reasoning to both deepen students' mathematical understanding and assist them recognize the social inequities that exist in both their personal and broader community (Harrison, 2015). *Considering global inequities, new problems provided by new media and communication practices, media manipulation, right-wing populism, climate crises, and intersectional discrimination, Social Justice offers a diversified and extensive perspective on how to make education more robust and meaningful.* Cochran-Smith (2004) notes that "social justice pedagogies refer to perspectives and academic traditions that actively confront the dynamics of privilege, oppression, and isms, acknowledging that social. Goals of teaching mathematics for social justice as discussed in Gutstein's framework are shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Gutstein's (2006) Model of Teaching Mathematics for Social Justice

The concern of this article will be on the social justice goal of teaching mathematics as shown the Figure 2. Furthermore, the three goals that comprise Gutstein's (2006) social pedagogical objectives are as explained.

Reading The World with Mathematics: By reading the world with mathematics, Gutstein is speaking of the application of mathematics to understand, investigate, and study problems that have an impact on students' immediate lives as well as the larger social realm.

Writing The World with Mathematics: writing the world with mathematics involves greater activity. Mathematicians who utilize the language of mathematics to transform the world are writing the world with mathematics.

Developing Positive Cultural and Social Identities: developing positive cultural identities demands teachers to respect and value the diverse cultural backgrounds of their pupils while also equipping them with the skills necessary to function well in the prevailing culture. There is a direct correlation between students' self-efficacy as social change agents and their ability to establish good social identities.

With all the goals as summarised in figure 2, same goal can be achieved with the African version of Social Justice Mathematics, in fact, there is no difference between social justice and ubuntu as a practice by Africans, hence the suggestion of ubuntuization in place of social justice mathematics. Ubuntuized mathematics classrooms is basically created to encourage student cooperation and a sense of unity in the pursuit of the teaching-learning objectives.

Ubuntuization

This is derived from the word ubuntu, which means our empathy and generosity for others define who we are. Anywhere that the term ubuntu is mentioned, justice, equity, peace and fairness is aboard. Ubuntu originates from the indigenous philosophy and knowledge of the Bantu people of Africa. This philosophy portrays human character as being grounded in spirituality, which reveals an individual's identity in relation to the universe and all forms of God's creation (Nxumalo & Mncube, 2019). Ubuntu is characterized as an inclusive philosophy that demands respect and dignity in our interactions with other people (Bolden, 2014; Mahaye, 2018; Makhanya and Mzinyane, 2023). Ubuntu lies at the heart of the African way of life and impacts on every aspect of people's well-being.

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Lefa (2019) and Letseka (2011) view ubuntu as a type of human interaction that promotes critical thinking, non-domination, and the best possible growth of interpersonal relationships. The type of human relationship encourage by ubuntu is same as equity and fairness in dealing with one another in all aspect of social life and in the classroom.

Ubuntu Pedagogy and Social Justice Mathematics

The application of the concept of ubuntu in the mathematics classroom does not only implies the utilization of ethnomathematics but also the humanisation of classroom to ensure equity, fairness, inclusiveness in the teaching of mathematics. Lefa (2019) and Msila (2008) opine that ubuntu signifies that a person is a person through other people and that ubuntu societies develop mechanisms to maintain social cohesion and harmony. They further expatiate that Ubuntu leads to the achievement of social justice in education because, for example, teachers who practice Ubuntu respect and value each student's needs and include them in their lessons. Blackwood(2018) sees the humanising approach to the teaching and engaging of students in the learning process as ubuntu pedagogy. An environment where learners are treated with dignity and affirmation, regardless of their ethnicity or class, is created by educators who use Ubuntu pedagogy (Ukpokodu 2016). The core tenet of Ubuntu pedagogy is that all students, regardless of their sexual orientation, race, educational background, or language proficiency, are human beings with the capacity to learn if their humanity is prioritized in both teaching and learning (Ngubane & Makua, 2021). Understanding and embracing Ubuntu ideals can probably provide instructors the confidence to use pedagogies that target all students in the classroom and fight injustice. Teachers that adopt the Ubuntu perspectives offer equitable opportunity for all students to grow and realize their full potential, regardless of their cultural, linguistic, social class, religion, or sexual orientation (Letseka, 2013). There is a relationship between ethnomathematics, social justice mathematics and the ubuntu pedagogy, they are all aimed at teaching mathematics justly, equitably and honestly to the students so as to enhance a boost in interest and achievement in mathematics.

Figure 3: Ubuntu pedagogy operational link in mathematics

All students are treated with respect and dignity in a classroom that embraces social justice and Ubuntu pedagogy, regardless of their background of the student, thus, enhancing justice and equity in the transmission of knowledge. Broodryk (2005) state that the goal of Ubuntu is to foster relationships between students and dismantle obstacles pertaining to diversity in the classroom. These objectives also align with social justice in education. For teaching of mathematics for social justice to be very effective and fully practice, ubuntu values should be first influenced as both works pari-passu. Thus, ubuntu can be seen as a tool that mathematics teachers can utilize to combat injustice and inequality in mathematics classrooms for an enhanced interest and achievement in mathematics.

Ubuntulised Mathematics Classroom

For a mathematics classroom to be effectively ubuntulised, the mathematics teacher needs to be fully equipped with the ubuntu philosophy whereby harmonious and positive relationship is encourage among the learners. Practicalizing the ubuntu in the mathematics classroom setting can be viewed as an ubutulised mathematics classroom. Kindness, compassion, unity, solidarity, collaboration, and sharing are all fostered by teaching and learning that is based on Ubuntu and that benefits both students and teachers by fostering positive relationships (Ukpokodu 2016)

Figure

Both and effective

trio has a

classroom where all the students will be treated respect and justly irrespective of the socio- cultural, socio-economic background, sex and learning capabilities (fast learner or slow learner). Students will turn be more interested in mathematics classrooms if they are being ubuntuised. In an ubuntuised mathematics classroom, given mathematical problems are solved with the aim of carrying all the students along devoid of sentiments and injustice. Practicalized example is given to students as to encourage them treating their colleagues justly.

Example 1: find the number of ways a social club in Pretoria(Y) can elect both a president and a secretary. Assume that all members are eligible, but that no one can hold both offices.

Solution

Let the five members of the club (Y) = {Junior, Khumalo, Lubanzi, Molekhule, Nkosi}

In short form; Y= {J, K, L, M, N}

Let's construct a table to enhanced clarity and understanding by all members of the class.

Table 1: Selection table

		SECRETARY				
		J	K	L	M	N
C H A I R M A N	J	*	JK	JL	JM	JN
	K	KJ	*	KL	KM	KN
	L	LJ	LK	*	LM	LN
	M	MJ	MK	ML	*	MN
	N	NJ	NK	NL	NM	*

Table 1 gives us the following list (for example, JK denotes president J and secretary K, while KJ denotes president K and secretary J): JK, JL, JM, JN, KJ, KL, KM, KN, LJ, LK, LM, LN, MJ, MK, ML, MN, NJ, NK, NL, NM.

Note: that certain entries are asterisk (*) from the table since the cases of JJ, KK, LL, MM and NN would imply one person holding both offices. From the above we can see that there are 20 possibilities of electing president and secretary.

These kinds of examples instil the spirit of fairness, equity, and justice in the learners, they see ubuntu being practicalized. In the process of solving the given problem, all the students were carried along and the steps involved were clearly explained such that slow learners too were carried along. Ubuntuised mathematics classroom also encourages group/ team learning and cooperative learning; whereby learners engage in solving given mathematical problems together devoid of gender, background and learning ability. Just as it is in the case of teaching mathematics for social justice where given problems are being practicalized in relation to our daily life activities, so, ubuntuization too does. Maphalala (2017) acknowledges the importance of ubuntu in the management of a classroom environment that is effective.

4: Structure of an Ubuntuised Mathematics Classroom

ethnomathematics, social justice mathematics ubuntuisation are geared towards making an mathematics classroom. In essence, a mathematics teacher that is equipped with the very high tendency of having an effective

Students' Interest and Achievement in Mathematics

When the right teaching approach is used in the teaching and learning of mathematics, students' interest is enhanced, and performance of students also improved. One of the crucial and attitudinal factors that predicts whether children will succeed in learning mathematics or not is interest (singh et al, 2002). The primary determinant of pupils' learning and academic performance is their level of interest (Age et al, 2021; Age & Machaba,2023). However, the issues of students' low interest and achievement in the topic are largely addressed by pedagogical improvements in learning facilitation (Khiwele & Mkomwa, 2022; Mazana et al,2019; peteros et al, 2020). Ubuntu classrooms are designed to foster an environment of academic achievement and advancement among students, so addressing this requires an understanding of the Ubuntu concept (Maphalala,2017). Omodan (2022) in a study concluded that when applied in the classroom, ubuntu and its derived presumptions will undoubtedly improve students' academic abilities by encouraging their performance, achievement, and overall development. Furthermore, Omodan and Tsotetsi (2019) clearly states that given that ubuntu in education is based on ideas like interdependence and community building via social interaction between teachers and students, it can be viewed as a method of instruction that promotes students' academic performance and growth.

Conclusion

In a quest of adhering to the tenants of ethnomathematics in proffering solution to the lack of interest and abysmal achievement of students in mathematics, this article has clearly unveiled the possibility of africanising the solution by adopting ubuntuization instead of social justice mathematics which afterwards have the same principles of equity and justice to the learners irrespective of the background, gender, culture and learning ability. Education through Ubuntu can contribute to the realization of social justice, for instance, teachers at schools respect, honor, value, and cater to the needs of every student. Ubuntu values must first have an impact on the school before it can implement social justice principles like equity, justice and respect for the learners of mathematics. This paper, therefore, recommend the ubuntuization of mathematics classrooms for the enhancement of students' interest and achievement in mathematics as championed by ethnomathematics projects in place of social justice mathematics since the latter is more indigenous and serves same purpose.

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